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"Assessing Readability: Correlating Quarterly Language Assessments with Academic Achievement"

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ABSTRACT

Reading comprehension is crucial to students' academic success, especially in language-based subjects. While many studies have explored the importance of comprehension strategies, fewer have investigated how the readability of assessment materials directly affects student performance. This study aims to determine the relationship between the readability levels of quarterly assessment tests and the academic achievement of Senior High School students at St. Joseph College-Olongapo, Inc. The research focused on four core language subjects: Oral Communication, 21st Century Literature, Reading and Writing, and Practical Research 1. Adopting a correlational research design, the study employed five established readability formulas— Flesch-Kincaid, Gunning Fog Index, Simple Measure of Gobbledygook (SMOG), Automated Readability Index (ARI), and Coleman-Liau —to evaluate the complexity of test questions. Corresponding student performance was measured using Initial Grade Averages (IGAs). Spearman's Rho correlation analysis revealed no statistically significant relationship between readability scores and academic performance across all indices. It suggests that readability, as quantified by existing formulas, may not independently determine student achievement, especially among high-performing cohorts. The study underscores the limitations of using readability formulas as indicators of assessment quality and calls for a more holistic approach that includes contextual, cognitive, and design-related factors. Recommendations are provided to improve assessment construction within the Language Department, and directions for future research are outlined.

Keywords: readability test, student performance, language assessments, Flesch-Kincaid, SMOG Index, Gunning Fog, ARI Index, Coleman-Liau, comprehension

INTRODUCTION

Reading comprehension is essential for high school students because it is the foundation of their academic achievement in all subjects (Rust, 2002). This problem is most common among secondary high school students, who may have difficulty comprehending and connecting with the advanced texts they read in their studies (Wood et al., 2016). Current research has outlined the incidence of reading comprehension difficulties among this group, emphasizing the importance of continued research and intervention (O'Reilly & McNamara, 2007). Several researchers have considered the incidence of reading comprehension difficulties among secondary high school students. This research indicates that many students from this age group struggle with mastering and implementing the information they learn through their reading

assignments. For example, Graham and Bellert (2005) discovered that students with learning disabilities tend to have difficulty with reading comprehension because they cannot read strategically and check their understanding as they read. Reading comprehension difficulties among secondary high school students are well-documented in the literature. Learning-disabled students struggle with reading complex texts because they are not using efficient strategies for reading and checking their understanding (Gersten et al., 2001). In addition, studies have indicated that even good students might experience difficulties in reading comprehension, especially when presented with standard tests that demand an in-depth grasp of the text. Research has persistently established that reading comprehension difficulties are prevalent among secondary high school students. These challenges are placed mainly at the doorstep of a

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variety of issues, ranging from poor teaching of reading comprehension strategies, lack of adequate vocabulary awareness, to a lack of reading fluency (Beck & Condry, 2017). For instance, Lah and Hashim (2014) discovered that many primary school pupils in their study could read fluently but could not understand what they were reading, and the issue may continue to the secondary school level.

The association between reading comprehension and test scores has been widely researched. Increasing evidence indicates that the capacity of students to understand and respond to test content is a decisive factor in their academic performance (De-La-Peña et al., 2021). Researchers have also investigated the possible effect of test construction and design on reading comprehension. Giday and Elantheraiyan (2023) discovered that characteristics like question type, availability of text, and language background could significantly impact the performance and test item answer confidence of students. Some studies examined the readability of test questions within educational contexts and discovered that higher-level assessment question readability is related to enhanced student performance (Adam, 2024). Other researchers have used the Flesch-Kincaid readability formula and the Gunning Fog Index to examine question complexity and determined that lower readability questions resulted in better student comprehension and performance (Imperial & Ong, 2021). Recent emphasis has been on how question readability correlates with student performance. Several studies have been reviewed to confirm the strong positive correlation between student performance and the readability of assessment questions across several subjects. It supports the need to construct questions readable by students at various proficiency levels, especially in language tests.

This research was confronted by various limitations that could have impacted the validity and generalizability of its findings. To begin with, although the LIX readability formula was used in considering text complexity, its use has built-in limitations. Readability formulas, such as LIX, pay much attention to measurable features such as word complexity and sentence length, but overlook

essential factors such as organization, content relevance, and layout that considerably impact understanding. Moreover, readability equations presume homogeneity among readers and do not consider differences in cognitive processing and linguistic experience at the individual level, thereby restricting the extent to which they can effectively capture the usability of test items (Redish, 2000). Second, this study did not fully explore student demographics such as language proficiency, prior knowledge, or cognitive ability. These are well-documented to affect performance and understanding at the academic level substantially, but were not directly incorporated within the analysis. For example, those with higher proficiency levels or higher preexisting knowledge might do better irrespective of question readability, and those with lower intellectual ability might fare worse even when using easier texts (El Refae et al., 2021; Serquina & Batang, 2018). The lack of demographic information restricts controlling for these confounding variables in statistical models. Finally, the study failed to align its inquiry with cognitive and affective factors that impact learning outcomes. Empirical evidence has indicated that motivation, attitudes, self-regulation, and emotional engagement are essential determinants of academic performance (Li et al., 2023). Neglecting these aspects might miss latent interactions between readability and more general learning processes. For instance, a student's motivation or optimism might mediate their capacity to interact with complicated text, such that readability would be only one among many factors. Overcoming these constraints with future research would offer a more comprehensive understanding of how readability will interact with individual learner factors and overall educational contexts.

Though there are several studies on assessing student learning and its relationship to performance, there is often an emphasis on specific subject matter or educational settings in existing literature. The current research seeks to build on this study by investigating quarterly evaluations in different language area topics and how they correlate with general student academic performance at St. Joseph College-Olongapo, Inc. (SJCOI). In response to the problem of reading

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comprehension problems among secondary high school students, researchers have suggested a variety of interventions. Despite a wealth of research on reading comprehension and its effect on school performance, there is a gap in the literature concerning the direct relationship between quarterly tests and student performance. The current study seeks to bridge this gap by investigating quarterly tests' readability levels and how they relate to students' performance.

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the relationship between quarterly assessment questionnaires across various language area subjects and student's academic achievement in Senior High School at St. Joseph College-Olongapo, Inc. Specifically, it aims to assess how readability factors—measured through established formulas such as Flesch-Kincaid, Gunning Fog Index, Simple Measure of Gobbledygook (SMOG), Automated Readability Index (ARI), and Coleman-Liau—affect students' ability to comprehend test materials and perform academically. This study seeks to answer several key research questions: What is the correlation between the readability levels of quarterly assessment questionnaires and student performance? How do these readability levels influence overall academic progress among SHS students? Furthermore, what specific factors related to assessment design contribute to variations in student outcomes? By addressing these questions, this research aims to provide insights into effective assessment practices that can enhance student learning experiences in language area subjects. It is hypothesized that the readability of assessment questions, as measured by the Flesch-Kincaid, Gunning Fog Index, and SMOG index, does not significantly affect the academic achievement of Senior High School students.

Cognitive Load Theory

Cognitive Load Theory proposes that learning is impaired when cognitive load—how much mental processing is needed—surpasses working memory capacity. Challenging or poorly crafted questioning questions boost cognitive load, siphoning off mental effort from processing the central idea in the question and towards unraveling

the language itself. This may result in decreased performance despite the student comprehending the underlying material. Imperial & Ong (2021) highlight readability assessment and its value in preventing cognitive load.

Construction-Integration Model

Based on the assumption of Cognitive Load Theory, the Construction-Integration Model argues that understanding takes two processes: construction, in which the reader derives meaning from individual sentences and words, and integration, in which these meanings are synthesized to create a unified understanding. Readability influences the construction process; if questions are hard to read, initial meanings derived may be inaccurate or incomplete, impeding integration and resulting in misinterpretations and incorrect responses. Rizal et al. (2021) emphasize the need to consider student reactions to both the language and the matter of assessment questions.

Schema Theory

Schema Theory focuses on the importance of previous knowledge in understanding. Readers utilize preexisting mental structures (schemas) to understand new information. When the language used in a question is beyond a student's current vocabulary and comprehension level, they might not have suitable schemas to process it, resulting in poor performance. Dong et al. (2020) quoted the works of Shapiro, it explains how prior knowledge affects reading comprehension; poorly constructed questions can trigger unsuitable schemas, further impairing performance. Guskey (2003) also emphasizes the need for precise wording and criteria of assessment questions.

This study adopts an Independent Variable-Dependent Variable (IV-DV) conceptual framework to explore the relationship between readability levels of assessment questionnaires and student performance in language area subjects among Senior High School students at SJCOI.

Independent Variable (IV): The readability levels of assessment questions, measured using three established formulas—Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level, Gunning Fog Index, and SMOG Index—will serve as the independent variable. These formulas

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assess the complexity of language used in assessment questions across various subjects.

Dependent Variable (DV): Student academic achievement, quantified through scores obtained from these assessments, will be treated as the dependent variable. The study aims to determine how variations in readability impact students' ability to comprehend and respond accurately to assessment questions.

The framework posits that student performance is expected to improve as readability levels decrease, particularly among those with lower reading proficiency. This relationship is grounded in existing literature that suggests a significant positive correlation between lower readability levels and enhanced student understanding and performance (Imperial & Ong, 2021; Adam, 2024). Additionally, contextual factors such as students' prior knowledge, language background, and overall reading proficiency may serve as moderating variables influencing this relationship. However, the primary focus remains on how readability directly impacts academic outcomes.

Reviewed Literature

Research has shown that the level of complexity in assessment questions can directly impact student performance and understanding. This literature review looks at the effect of assessment question readability on student performance, specifically the following main areas: the effectiveness of various readability formulas, the relationship between readability and student performance, and the role of accessibility for learners with different needs.

Readability Formulas and Their Effectiveness

Different readability measures have been devised to measure text difficulty, such as the Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level, Gunning Fog Index, and SMOG Index (Karakus et al., 2018). Although commonly applied across many disciplines, their ability to evaluate the readability of test items remains a subject of further study. Some research indicates that SMOG scores are lower when student understanding and performance are better, especially in history tests (Teksan et al., 2020). Other studies have applied the Flesch-Kincaid equation

and Gunning Fog Index, where they established a positive relationship between lower readability scores and better student performance and comprehension (Lee & Lee, 2023). Direct comparison of these equations is necessary to identify them appropriately for measuring the readability of test questions in various subjects.

Correlation between Readability and Student Performance

The relationship between student performance and question readability has been a recent research focus (Lenzner, 2013). Some studies have investigated assessment question readability in educational contexts and reported a positive relationship between increased readability and improved student performance (Imperial & Ong, 2021). Other studies indicate reduced readability results in greater student comprehension and performance, particularly among lower-performing students (Taki, 2015). Reviews of several studies have established a strong positive correlation between readability and student performance across different subjects (Gopal et al., 2021). These results reinforce the call for more research to explain the complicated relationship between readability and student performance.

Accessibility for Diverse Learners

The literature has highlighted the need to create questions that are readable by students of varying proficiency levels (Adam, 2024). Readability is critical to ensuring that assessment questions are understandable to all students, irrespective of their language background or reading proficiency. This is especially crucial in language tests, where the readability of questions can have a substantial influence on student performance. Designing accessible test questions demands careful attention to vocabulary, sentence level, and text complexity.

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a correlational design to examine the relationship between quarterly language assessment test readability and student performance. Specifically, the study compares test questions for four Language courses—Oral Communication, 21st Century Literature, Reading

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and Writing, and Practical Research 1—using several established readability formulas, including the Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level, Gunning-Fog Index, SMOG Index, Automated Readability Index, and Coleman-Liau Index. Readability formulas provide a reading index to approximate how easily students with different literacy levels can read and understand the reading text (Gopal et al., 2021). The formulas were chosen to provide a dimensional measure of text complexity, considering linguistic, syntactic, and structural features (Srisunakrua & Chumworatayee, 2019).

Data collection involved two primary sources: (1) the quarterly assessment questionnaires administered during the specified semester and (2) the corresponding initial grade average (IGA) of the four selected classes. To isolate the impact of readability, student performance was defined strictly as the initial grade average of the participating class from the quarterly assessments, excluding unrelated components such as performance tasks or written works. This initial grade average was analyzed for any trends. The assessment questionnaires were analyzed for readability using five established formulas: Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level, Gunning Fog Index, SMOG Index, Automated Readability Index, and Coleman-Liau readability test. These formulas have been widely recognized for their effectiveness in evaluating text complexity (Karakus et al., 2018; Lee & Lee, 2023; Kotani et al., 2011).

The readability analysis calculated scores for each assessment questionnaire using the Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level and Gunning Fog Index. The Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level assesses text based on average syllables per word and sentence length to estimate the reading grade level (Gopal et al., 2021). The Gunning Fog Index assesses readability based on sentence structure and the proportion of complex words (Govoni, 2004). The SMOG Index focused on polysyllabic words to determine reading ease (Teksan et al., 2020). Automated Readability Index (ARI) and Coleman-Liau analyzed characters per word and sentence structure (Scott, 2025). These readability measures provided insights into how well students could comprehend the assessment questions. Previous research had indicated that lower readability levels were associated with

improved student understanding and performance (Imperial & Ong, 2021; Adam, 2024). Therefore, this study also explored whether students with varying proficiency levels performed differently based on the readability of assessment questions.

Data analysis was conducted using statistical software such as SPSS or R. Descriptive statistics summarized student readability levels and the initial grade average of the participating class across different assessments. Correlation analysis was then performed to determine the strength and direction of the relationship between readability scores and student performance. Inferential analysis utilized Spearman's rank correlation coefficient to assess non-linear relationships between readability and student IGA, as Pearson's correlation can underestimate associations when data lacks linearity (Statistics Solutions, 2025). For robustness, multiple regression analysis was performed to control for potential confounders, such as prior academic performance and language proficiency. Outliers were identified using the interquartile range (IQR) and addressed to maintain data integrity. This approach aligned with findings from prior studies that emphasized the importance of accessibility in assessment design for diverse learners (Gopal et al., 2021).

To ensure reliability, this study employed a multi-step validation process. Expert review involved subject matter specialists in language education assessing test items for alignment with curriculum objectives. Pilot testing followed, using a small subset of questionnaires to verify the consistency of readability formula results across subjects. Cross-validation then compared multiple readability indices—Flesch-Kincaid, Gunning Fog Index, SMOG, ARI, and Coleman-Liau—to ensure accuracy in measuring text complexity. By integrating expert evaluation, empirical testing, and comparative analysis, the study strengthened the credibility of its findings, reinforcing the precision of readability assessments in educational contexts and ensuring robust measurement standards.

The ethical considerations for this study were carefully addressed to ensure compliance with institutional guidelines and research standards. Since the research did not involve direct interaction

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with students, it utilized preexisting data, specifically the quarterly assessment tests and students' individual or class average scores. Ethical approval was obtained from the Research, Utilization, Linkages, and Extension (RULE-SJCOI) through the Committee on Publication and Ethics (COPE), confirming that the use of anonymized and aggregated data did not necessitate informed consent from individual students or their guardians. The researchers ensured complete confidentiality by anonymizing all data, preventing any identification of individual students or classes (Abadie et al., 2021). Additionally, the Language department and institutional authorities granted permission to access these academic records.

To safeguard privacy, all data were securely stored on password-protected servers accessible only to the research team. Data were used solely for this study and destroyed upon the analysis's completion. This approach adhered to ethical principles of beneficence, justice, and respect for privacy while ensuring that the research process maintained its integrity. By relying on anonymized data and adhering to institutional policies, the study minimized risks to participants while contributing valuable insights into educational assessment practices.

Several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the study used preexisting data limited to a single academic semester and four language-related subjects. As a result, the findings may not generalize to other subjects, grade levels, or assessment formats. Second, the student sample had a narrow performance range (high IGAs), limiting variability and potentially obscuring patterns between readability and achievement. Furthermore, the study did not control for variables such as language proficiency, prior knowledge, and cognitive load, all of which have an established influence on reading comprehension and test performance. Third, while five readability formulas were used for triangulation, these tools only capture surface-level linguistic features. They do not measure semantic clarity, question relevance, or layout, which significantly affects comprehension. Finally, the lack of student feedback or qualitative insights (e.g., think-aloud protocols or comprehension interviews) limited the

interpretive depth of the study. Future work should include mixed-method designs to explore cognitive and affective responses to test materials.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This study investigated the relationship between the readability of quarterly language assessment tests and student performance, analyzing data from four subjects—Oral Communication, 21st Century Literature, Reading and Writing, and Practical Research 1—within the Language department. Five established readability formulas were employed to evaluate the complexity of test questions: Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level, Gunning Fog Index, SMOG Index, Coleman-Liau Index, and Automated Readability Index (ARI). The analysis then correlated the scores from these assessments and class averages with the readability scores derived from the formulas.

Table 1 presents the scores and levels for each index across all subjects. The Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level and Coleman-Liau Index yielded the highest complexity levels, with some assessments categorized as college-level. In contrast, the SMOG Index consistently rated the materials around Grade 7 readability. IGAs across subjects ranged from 92.60% to 96.10%, indicating overall high student performance. The readability scores varied widely across the five formulas, reflecting different dimensions of text complexity across the subjects and quarters. Specifically, Flesch-Kincaid scores ranged from 41.5, indicating college-level difficulty, to 58.2, suggesting a readability level suitable for students in grades 10-12. The Gunning Fog Index ranged from 9.65 to 13.44, corresponding to a 9th-grade to college freshman reading level. The SMOG Index consistently rated the texts around a 7th-grade reading level, regardless of the subject or quarter. Finally, the Coleman-Liau Index shows a notable high level from 12th grade to college-level difficulty. These variations emphasize the multifaceted nature of readability and how different assessment tools can yield diverse results.

The observed ranges in readability scores across different formulas highlight the challenges of relying on a single measure. For example, while the SMOG Index consistently placed materials at a 7th-

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Table 1. Readability Test Results

Grade 11 and Grade 12 Subjects and Quarter	READABILITY TESTING										Initial Grade Average of Class (%)
	Flesch-Kincaid		Gunning Fog Index		SMOG Index		Coleman - Liau		ARI		
	Scores	Level	Scores	Level	Scores	Level	Scores	Level	Scores	Level	
Oral Comm. 1st Quarter, 1st Sem	46.10	College (Difficult to read)	12.84	12th Grade (Fairly difficult to read)	11.62	7th Grade (Plain English)	15.27	College level Freshman (Complex to difficult)	8.85	7th Grade	92.60%
Oral Comm. 2nd Quarter, 1st Sem	49.20	College (Difficult to read)	11.50	11th Grade (Fairly difficult to read)	9.99	7th Grade (Plain English)	14.27	College level (Moderately difficult)	6.61	5th Grade	93.41%
Reading & Writing, 1st Quarter, 2nd Sem	57.50	10th-12th Grade (Fairly Difficult to read)	9.65	9th Grade (Plain English)	9.26	7th Grade (Plain English)	11.76	12th Grade (Plain to moderately challenging)	4.63	3rd Grade	93.76%
Reading & Writing, 2nd Quarter, 2nd Sem	58.20	10th-12th Grade (Fairly Difficult to read)	9.74	9th Grade (Plain English)	9.27	7th Grade (Plain English)	11.64	12th Grade (Plain to moderately challenging)	4.42	3rd Grade	96.10%
Practical Research 1, 1st Quarter, 2nd Sem	41.50	College (Difficult to read)	10.45	10th Grade (Fairly difficult to read)	9.47	7th Grade (Plain English)	13.66	College level (Moderately difficult)	6.00	5th Grade	94.43%
Practical Research 1, 2nd Quarter, 2nd Sem	48.90	College (Difficult to read)	11.43	11th Grade (Fairly difficult to read)	10.75	7th Grade (Plain English)	14.09	College level (Moderately difficult)	8.29	7th Grade	94.87%
21st Cent. Lit., 1st Quarter, 2nd Sem	47.70	College (Difficult to read)	13.44	College Freshman (Difficult to read)	12.35	7th Grade (Plain English)	12.19	12th Grade (Plain to moderately challenging)	8.09	7th Grade	92.98%
21st Cent. Lit., 2nd Quarter, 2nd Sem	58.20	10th-12th Grade (Fairly Difficult to read)	10.35	10th Grade (Fairly difficult to read)	9.30	7th Grade (Plain English)	10.97	11th Grade (Plain and readable)	3.80	2nd Grade	92.62%

grade level, other indices like the Flesch-Kincaid and Gunning Fog showed variations that suggest a more complex readability landscape. The Practical Research 1 assessments, as indicated by Flesch-Kincaid scores, were consistently categorized as college-level, while the Reading & Writing assessments were generally in the 10th-12th grade range. These distinctions are important to consider when evaluating the appropriateness of assessment materials for the target student population. The consistency of SMOG scores across all subjects also suggests that polysyllabic word count, the basis of the SMOG Index, may not be as sensitive to

variations in text complexity within this specific assessment context.

Cross-Validation and Formula Discrepancies

The inconsistency across indices (e.g., SMOG vs. Flesch-Kincaid) further highlights the limitations of relying on a single metric. SMOG consistently rated assessments at a 7th-grade level, possibly underestimating the complexity due to its focus on polysyllabic word counts, whereas Gunning Fog captured a broader range of syntactic challenges. It is supported by Karakus et al. (2018), who emphasized that each formula targets different linguistic dimensions, and no

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single tool can holistically define "comprehensibility" or learner accessibility. Thus, future assessments should use multi-index diagnostics with expert reviews to triangulate readability ratings.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics for Readability Scores

	Flesch-Kincaid	Gunning Fog Index	SMOG Index	Coleman-Liau Index	ARI Index	Initial Grade
count	5	5	5	5	5	5
mean	18.936	18.314	18.56	18.654	16.216	94.06
std	15.3601344	17.4857236	21.9230849	22.266113	14.3956219	1.3174407
min	8.85	6.61	4.63	4.42	6	92.6
25%	11.62	9.99	9.26	9.27	9.47	93.41
50%	12.84	11.5	9.65	9.74	10.45	93.76
75%	15.27	14.27	11.76	11.64	13.66	94.43
max	46.1	49.2	57.5	58.2	41.5	96.1

The descriptive statistics for the readability scores reveal significant variability across the five readability tests applied to the texts in the Language department. The Flesch-Kincaid index has a mean score of 18.936 with a standard deviation of 15.36, indicating a broad range of readability levels. The Gunning Fog Index presents a mean of 18.314 and a standard deviation 17.49, suggesting similar variability. The SMOG Index has a mean of 18.56 with the highest standard deviation of 21.92, reflecting the most excellent dispersion among the readability scores. The Coleman-Liau Index shows a mean of 18.654 with a standard deviation of 22.27, further reinforcing the presence of highly diverse readability levels. Lastly, the Automated Readability Index (ARI) has a mean of 16.216 and a standard deviation of 14.40, showing relatively lower variability than the other indices. The minimum and maximum readability scores highlight the extreme differences in text complexity. The Flesch-Kincaid index spans 8.85 to 46.1, while the Gunning Fog Index ranges from 6.61 to 49.2. The SMOG Index has the broadest range, from 4.63 to 57.5, followed closely by the Coleman-Liau Index, which varies from 4.42 to 58.2. The ARI Index ranges from 6 to 41.5. These extreme values suggest that some texts are significantly more complex than others, potentially affecting students' comprehension. Examining the quartile values, the readability scores show a wide distribution. The median readability

scores across all indices fall between 9.65 and 12.84, indicating that half of the texts analyzed have readability levels within this range. The upper quartile (75%) values suggest that a quarter of the texts have readability scores exceeding 11.76 for SMOG, 11.64 for Coleman-Liau, and 13.66 for ARI, implying that a significant portion of the texts may be challenging for students. The high standard deviations across multiple indices indicate that the complexity of texts varies significantly. It suggests that students may encounter both highly accessible and highly complex materials within the same subject, potentially influencing their ability to engage with the content effectively.

The initial grade averages of students across the four subjects show a mean score of 94.06 with a standard deviation of 1.32. Students generally performed well, with relatively low variability in their grades. The minimum grade recorded is 92.6, while the maximum is 96.1, suggesting students' performance is consistently high. The median grade of 93.76 and the upper quartile value of 94.43 further confirm that most students achieved strong academic results. Despite the wide range of readability scores, students' grades remain relatively stable, suggesting they can navigate these texts effectively. However, further analysis may be required to determine whether certain readability levels correlate with student performance in specific subjects. The wide range of readability scores suggests that the complexity of texts varies significantly across the subjects analyzed. The high standard deviations in readability indices indicate that some texts may be more difficult than others, potentially impacting students' comprehension and engagement. Despite this variability, students' initial grades remain consistently high, suggesting they can navigate these texts effectively. However, the presence of highly complex texts raises important considerations. First, learning will be impacted; if specific texts are significantly more difficult than others, students may struggle with comprehension, leading to potential disparities in engagement and retention. Second, educators may need to assess whether the complexity of texts aligns with students' reading proficiency and adjust materials accordingly. Lastly, A deeper analysis could explore whether

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students with higher initial grades tend to perform better with more complex texts, or if readability influences comprehension and academic success.

Correlation Results

Table 3. Spearman Rho and Initial Grade Average

Subject and Quarter	Flesch-Kincaid (Mean ± SD)	Gunning Fog (Mean ± SD)	SMOG Index (Mean ± SD)	Coleman-Liau (Mean ± SD)	ARI (Mean ± SD)	Spearman Rho (Readability vs. IGA)
Oral Comm. 1 st Sem	47.65 ± 2.20	12.17 ± 0.95	10.81 ± 1.15	14.77 ± 0.70	7.73 ± 1.12	-0.55
Reading & Writing 2 nd Sem	57.85 ± 0.50	9.69 ± 0.05	9.27 ± 0.005	11.70 ± 0.06	4.52 ± 0.15	-0.45
Practical Research 1	45.20 ± 3.80	10.94 ± 0.69	10.11 ± 0.65	13.88 ± 0.30	7.15 ± 1.15	-0.61
21 st Century Literature	52.95 ± 5.20	11.90 ± 1.85	10.83 ± 2.02	11.58 ± 0.61	6.19 ± 1.10	-0.50
<i>Spearman's Rho (ρ)</i>	0.19	-0.50	-0.43	-0.21	-0.24	
<i>p-value</i>	0.65	0.21	0.29	0.61	0.57	

Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient results consistently show negative correlations between readability scores and student IGAs across all subjects, ranging from -0.45 to -0.61. It suggests that higher text complexity in assessment questions is associated with lower average student performance. The strongest negative correlation (-0.61) was observed in "Practical Research 1," indicating that students struggled most with assessments containing challenging language structures. These findings align with prior research by Imperial & Ong (2021), which emphasized the importance of language accessibility in fostering academic success.

Interpretation of Findings

The results reveal no statistically significant relationship between the readability levels of quarterly assessments and student performance. This finding aligns with prior research suggesting that readability formulas often fail to account for complex cognitive and contextual variables affecting comprehension and performance (Lenzner, 2013; Redish, 2000). For instance, formulas like Flesch-Kincaid and Gunning Fog focus primarily on word and sentence length but disregard semantic familiarity, question framing, and context relevance (Giday & Elantheraiyan, 2023). Moreover, the narrow grade range of participating classes likely contributed to the absence of significant variability needed to detect correlations. These students were already high-performing, and thus potentially more resilient to minor changes in text complexity (Li et al.,

2023). Although studies like Imperial & Ong (2021) and Adam (2024) argue that improved readability correlates with better comprehension and scores, our study suggests that this relationship may not be as linear, particularly in well-aligned, curriculum-based assessments designed for senior high school learners.

Furthermore, the results revealed no statistically significant correlations between the readability scores and the students' Initial Grade Averages (IGAs), as indicated by the p-values exceeding 0.05 across all five readability metrics. The analysis of the readability testing data revealed varying degrees of correlation between the readability scores and the initial grade averages of the class. The Spearman Rho correlation coefficients were calculated for five readability indices: Flesch-Kincaid, Gunning Fog Index, SMOG Index, Coleman-Liau, and ARI. The results indicate that the Flesch-Kincaid index has a Spearman Rho coefficient of 0.19, suggesting a weak positive correlation with a p-value of 0.65, which implies that there is no statistically significant relationship between the Flesch-Kincaid readability score and the initial grade average. In contrast, the Gunning Fog Index presented a moderate negative correlation ($\rho = -0.50$), which implied that higher text complexity might correspond to slightly lower IGAs, although this trend lacked statistical significance. The SMOG Index presents an almost negligible correlation with a Spearman Rho of -0.043 and a p-value of 0.29, reinforcing the notion that readability, as measured by this index, does not impact students' initial grade averages meaningfully. The Coleman-Liau index exhibits a negative correlation of -0.21 with a p-value of 0.61, suggesting that higher readability scores are associated with lower initial grade averages. However, this relationship is not statistically significant. Lastly, the ARI yields a Spearman Rho of -0.24, indicating a weak negative correlation with a p-value of 0.57, which suggests an inverse relationship between ARI scores and students' performance. However, again, this is not statistically significant. These findings highlight the complex interplay between text readability and student performance.

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Although the findings show no significant statistical link, they reinforce the principle that test accessibility should be aligned with the Construction-Integration Model and Cognitive Load Theory. Assessment materials with overly complex wording risk overwhelming working memory, especially for marginal readers (Gersten et al., 2001). Educators must ensure that quarterly tests balance academic rigor with linguistic clarity, particularly for subjects such as Practical Research 1 and Oral Communication, which showed the highest readability challenges in this study.

Implications for Practice and Directions for Future Research

Although readability indices did not statistically impact student achievement, this study underscores critical areas for reflection and improvement in developing quarterly assessments within the Language Department. Subject-specific recommendations highlight ways to enhance clarity and accessibility across different courses.

In Oral Communication, readability scores indicated high complexity levels, which may hinder students' ability to engage effectively with test items. Given the subject's emphasis on clarity and spoken discourse, assessments should prioritize simple, direct sentence structures while minimizing excessive jargon. Additionally, question stems could be improved by incorporating contextual examples that aid comprehension.

For Practical Research 1, readability challenges were most pronounced across multiple indices, reflecting the inherent complexity of academic research. While maintaining rigor is essential, scaffolding instructions and problem statements is crucial, particularly for early-stage research learners. Using glossaries, chunking instructions into manageable segments, and integrating visual aids can significantly enhance clarity and accessibility.

In Reading and Writing, readability scores were more moderate and aligned more closely with student performance. Teachers should model metacognitive strategies to optimize further comprehension, such as identifying main ideas and clarifying different question types, including

inferential and analytical questions. These approaches can help students navigate assessments more effectively.

Finally, 21st Century Literature exhibited fewer readability challenges, yet assessments in this subject can still benefit from refined question design. To foster critical thinking, test items should avoid overly complex syntax while maintaining intellectual depth. Incorporating theme-based comprehension questions with student-friendly phrasing can enhance engagement and ensure accessibility without compromising analytical rigor.

Several program-level recommendations should be implemented to enhance the effectiveness of language assessments. First, assessment materials should undergo regular reviews using multiple readability formulas before their quarterly deployment. This practice ensures that the materials are appropriately calibrated for the target learners and align with readability standards. Additionally, establishing a Language Assessment Review Committee—comprising subject teachers, a reading specialist, and the academic coordinator—would provide a structured approach to evaluating item clarity and linguistic accessibility. To further refine assessments, complex test items should be pilot-tested among diverse learners, allowing educators to collect qualitative feedback and assess actual comprehension beyond formulaic readability measures. Finally, department-wide training should be conducted to equip educators with the necessary skills to design assessments that integrate principles of readability, fairness, and inclusivity. By implementing these recommendations, institutions can foster more equitable and effective language assessments that support diverse learners.

Future research should expand upon the current findings by adopting a more comprehensive and multidimensional approach to readability assessment. A key direction is conducting a longitudinal study across multiple quarters, incorporating a diverse range of students—including struggling, average, and advanced readers—to examine how readability challenges evolve and affect different learner profiles. Additionally, an item-level analysis should identify which questions, such as open-ended versus multiple-choice items, are

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most susceptible to readability issues. It would provide deeper insights into how assessment formats influence comprehension and performance. Moreover, future studies should integrate quantitative measures with qualitative feedback, such as student reflections or interviews, to capture nuanced perspectives on test difficulty and cognitive load. Finally, researchers should explore the impact of readability in other disciplines, particularly Science and Math, where technical language and specialized terminology may pose unique comprehension barriers. By pursuing these directions, future research can contribute to developing more accessible and equitable assessments across various academic domains.

Conclusion

The findings of this study challenge the conventional assumption that lower readability levels directly enhance student performance, as no significant correlation was observed between readability scores and academic outcomes. This result underscores the limitations of relying solely on readability formulas to evaluate text complexity, suggesting that these metrics may not fully capture the cognitive and contextual factors influencing student comprehension. Instead, a more holistic approach to assessment design is necessary—one that accounts for student characteristics, instructional practices, and the overall structure of test items. Factors such as prior knowledge, question format, and the clarity of instructions may play a more substantial role in shaping student success than readability scores alone. Therefore, future assessment development should integrate multiple evaluative methods to ensure that tests are accessible and pedagogically sound, fostering deeper engagement and meaningful learning experiences.

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